

Supplementary Table S1. The designed primer information for PCR amplification of the *granzyme g* promoter deletion constructs in this study

Primer sets ¹	Oligonucleotide sequence (5'-to-3')	T _m (°C)
Gzmg promoter FL_F	CGACATGTGAATTTACAACCAGAGTCAT	58
Gzmg promoter FL_R	TACTCGAGGAGGGCAGAGCAGACAC	60
Gzmg promoter Δ1_F	ACATGTAAGAATGGGCTACATGACTAAT	60
Gzmg promoter Δ2_F	ACATGTGCAATACTGTAGGAAATACCAC	60
Gzmg promoter Δ3_F	ACATGTCAGAGATAAATGACAATACCCA	60
Gzmg promoter Δ4_F	ACATGTTACTGTGGAAC TTTGAGAGTG	60
ΔStat3mut_F	TACTTGTGTGCAGCCACTGTCTCAGACCTC CTCAACCACAACC	84.9
ΔStat3mut_R	GGTTGTGGTTGAGGAGGTCTGAGACAGTG GCTGCACACAAGTA	84.9

¹F: forward primer; R: reverse primer